

New Bounds of the First Zagreb Index and Some Hamiltonian Properties of Graphs

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Abstract

The first Zagreb index of a graph is defined as the sum of the squares of the degrees of vertices in the graph. In this note, we obtain new lower and upper bounds for the first Zagreb index of a graph. Using the new bounds, we present sufficient conditions based on the first Zagreb index for some Hamiltonian properties of a graph.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges. The degree of a vertex v is denoted by $d_G(v)$. We use δ and Δ to denote the minimum degree and maximum degree of G , respectively. A set of vertices in a graph G

is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of the largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . We use $K_{p,q}$ to denote a complete bipartite graph in which the two partition sets have cardinalities of p and q , respectively. For disjoint vertex subsets X and Y of $V(G)$, we use $E(X, Y)$ to denote the set of all the edges in $E(G)$ such that one end vertex of each edge is in X and another end vertex of the edge is in Y . Namely, $E(X, Y) := \{e : e = xy \in E, x \in X, y \in Y\}$. A cycle C in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian cycle of G if C contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called Hamiltonian if G has a Hamiltonian cycle. A path P in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian path of G if P contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called traceable if G has a Hamiltonian path. Often, researchers are interested in finding new sufficient conditions for the Hamiltonian and traceable graphs.

In 1972, Gutman and Trinajstić [4] introduced the definition of the first Zagreb index of a graph. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index, denoted $M_1(G)$, is defined as $\sum_{u \in V(G)} d_G^2(u)$. The first Zagreb index has been intensively investigated in the last several decades. Researchers obtained a lot of results on the first Zagreb index. One can find the results in the survey paper [3] and the references therein. From the survey paper [3] and the references therein, we can see that finding the bounds for the first Zagreb index is one of the important topics in the research on the first Zagreb index. In this note, we obtain new lower and upper bounds for the first Zagreb of a graph. Using the new bounds, we present sufficient conditions based on the first Zagreb index for Hamiltonian and traceable graphs. Below are the main results in this paper.

Theorem 1. Let G be a graph with n vertices and e edges. Suppose I is an independent set in G such that $|I| < n$. Define $\Delta_1 = \max\{d(x) : x \in I\}$ and $\delta_1 = \min\{d(y) : y \in V - I\}$. Then

[1]. $M_1(G) \leq \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2$ with equality if and only if G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $d(u) = \Delta_1$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \Delta$ for each v in $V - I$.

[2]. $M_1(G) \geq \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2$ with equality if and only if G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $d(u) = \delta$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \delta_1$ for each v in $V - I$.

Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices and e edges. Suppose I is any independent set in G of size $(k + 1)$ with $\Delta_1 = \max\{d(x) : x \in I\}$ and $\delta_1 = \min\{d(y) : y \in V - I\}$.

[1]. If $M_1(G) \geq \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2$, then G is Hamiltonian or G is $K_{k, k+1}$.

[2]. $M_1(G) \leq \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2$, then G is Hamiltonian or G is $K_{k, k+1}$.

Theorem 3. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 1$) graph with $n \geq 9$ vertices and e edges. Suppose I is any independent set in G of size $(k + 2)$ with $\Delta_1 = \max\{d(x) : x \in I\}$ and $\delta_1 = \min\{d(y) : y \in V - I\}$.

[1]. If $M_1(G) \geq \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2$, then G is traceable or G is $K_{k, k+2}$.

[2]. $M_1(G) \leq \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2$, then G is traceable or G is $K_{k, k+2}$.

2 Lemmas

We will use the following results as our lemmas. The first two are from [2].

Lemma 1 [2]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order $n \geq 3$. If $\beta \leq k$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Lemma 2 [2]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order n . If $\beta \leq k + 1$, then G is traceable.

Lemma 2.3 below is from [6].

Lemma 3 [6]. Let G be a balanced bipartite graph of order $2n$ with bipartition (A, B) . If $d(x) + d(y) \geq n + 1$ for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in B$ with $xy \notin E$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Lemma 2.4 below is from [5].

Lemma 4 [5]. Let G be a 2-connected bipartite graph with bipartition (A, B) , where $|A| \geq |B|$. If each vertex in A has degree at least s and each vertex in B has degree at least t , then G contains a cycle of length at least $2 \min(|B|, s + t - 1, 2s - 2)$.

3 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1.1. Let G be a graph with n vertices and e edges. Let $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{|I|}\}$ be an independent set in G such that $|I| < n$. Then

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = |E(I, V - I)| \leq \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v).$$

Since $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) + \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v) = 2e$, we have that

$$\sum_{u \in I} d(u) \leq e \leq \sum_{v \in V - I} d(v).$$

Proof of [1] in Theorem 1.

Now we have that

$$\sum_{u \in I} d^2(u) \leq \Delta_1 \sum_{u \in I} d(u) \leq \Delta_1 e.$$

Therefore

$$M_1(G) = \sum_{w \in V} d^2(w) = \sum_{u \in I} d^2(u) + \sum_{v \in V - I} d^2(v) \leq \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2.$$

If

$$M_1(G) = \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2,$$

we, from the proofs above, have that $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e$ which implies that $\sum_{v \in V - I} d(v) = e$ and G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$. Furthermore, we have that $d(u) = \Delta_1$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \Delta$ for each $v \in V - I$.

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If G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $d(u) = \Delta_1$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \Delta$ for each vertex v in $V - I$, then $e = \Delta_1|I| = (n - |I|)\Delta$. A simple computation shows that

$$M_1(G) = \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2.$$

This completes the proof of [1] in Theorem 1.

Proof of [2] in Theorem 1.

Now we have that

$$\sum_{v \in V-I} d^2(v) \geq \delta_1 \sum_{v \in V-I} d(v) \geq \delta_1 e.$$

Therefore

$$M_1(G) = \sum_{w \in V} d^2(w) = \sum_{u \in I} d^2(u) + \sum_{v \in V-I} d^2(v) \geq \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2.$$

If

$$M_1(G) = \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2,$$

we, from the proofs above, have that $\sum_{v \in V-I} d(v) = e$ which implies that $\sum_{u \in I} d(u) = e$ and G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$. Furthermore, we have that $d(u) = \delta$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \delta_1$ for each $v \in V - I$.

If G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $d(u) = \delta$ for each $u \in I$ and $d(v) = \delta_1$ for each vertex v in $V - I$, then $e = \delta_1(n - |I|) = |I|\delta$. A simple computation shows that

$$M_1(G) = \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2.$$

This completes the proof of [1] in Theorem 1.

Proof of [1] in Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices and e edges satisfying the conditions in [1] in Theorem 2. If $\beta \leq k$, then Lemma 1 implies that G is Hamiltonian. Now we assume that $\beta \geq (k + 1)$. Then G has an independent set I of size $(k + 1)$. Suppose G is

not Hamiltonian. We have that $n \geq 2\delta + 1 \geq 2k + 1$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq n/2$ and G is Hamiltonian. From the conditions in [1] in Theorem 2 and Theorem 1, we have

$$\Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2 \leq M_1(G) \leq \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2,$$

where $\Delta_1 = \max\{d(x) : x \in I\}$.

Thus

$$M_1(G) = \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2.$$

Therefore G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $|I| = (k + 1)$, $d(u) = \Delta_1$ for each $u \in I$, and $d(v) = \Delta$ for each vertex v in $V - I$. Since $\Delta_1 |I| = e = (n - |I|)\Delta$ and $\Delta_1 \leq \Delta$, we have $n - |I| \leq |I| = k + 1$. Notice that $n - |I| \geq k$, we have that $n - |I| = k$ or $n - |I| = (k + 1)$. If $n - |I| = k$, then G is $K_{k, k+1}$. If $n - |I| = (k + 1)$, then Lemma 3 implies that G is Hamiltonian, a contradiction.

This completes the proof of [1] in Theorem 2.

Proof of [2] in Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices and e edges satisfying the conditions in [2] in Theorem 2. If $\beta \leq k$, then Lemma 1 implies that G is Hamiltonian. Now we assume that $\beta \geq (k + 1)$. Then G has an independent set I of size $(k + 1)$. Suppose G is not Hamiltonian. We have that $n \geq 2\delta + 1 \geq 2k + 1$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq n/2$ and G is Hamiltonian. From the conditions in [2] in Theorem 2 and Theorem 1, we have

$$\delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2 \leq M_1(G) \leq \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2,$$

where $\delta_1 = \min\{d(y) : y \in V - I\}$.

Thus

$$M_1(G) = \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2.$$

Therefore G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $|I| = (k + 1)$, $d(u) = \delta$ for each $u \in I$, and $d(v) = \delta_1$ for each vertex v in $V - I$. Since $\delta |I| = e = (n - |I|)\delta_1$ and $\delta_1 \geq \delta$, we have $n - |I| \leq |I| = k + 1$. Notice that $n - |I| \geq k$, we have that $n - |I| = k$ or $n - |I| = (k + 1)$. If $n - |I| = k$, then G is $K_{k, k+1}$. If $n - |I| = (k + 1)$, then Lemma 3 implies

that G is Hamiltonian, a contradiction.

This completes the proof of [2] in Theorem 2.

Proof of [1] in Theorem 3. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 1$) graph with $n \geq 9$ vertices and e edges satisfying the conditions in [1] in Theorem 3. If $\beta \leq k + 1$, then Lemma 2 implies that G is traceable. Now we assume that $\beta \geq (k + 2)$. Then G has an independent set I of size $(k + 2)$. Suppose G is not traceable. We have that $n \geq 2\delta + 2 \geq 2k + 2$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq (n - 1)/2$ and G is traceable. From the conditions in [1] in Theorem 3 and Theorem 1, we have

$$\Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2 \leq M_1(G) \leq \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2.$$

where $\Delta_1 = \max\{d(x) : x \in I\}$.

Thus

$$M_1(G) = \Delta_1 e + (n - |I|)\Delta^2.$$

Therefore G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $|I| = (k + 2)$, $d(u) = \Delta_1$ for each $u \in I$, and $d(v) = \Delta$ for each vertex v in $V - I$. Since $\Delta_1 |I| = e = (n - |I|)\Delta$ and $\Delta_1 \leq \Delta$, we have $n - |I| \leq |I| = k + 2$. Notice that $n - |I| \geq k$, we have that $n - |I| = k$, $n - |I| = (k + 1)$, or $n - |I| = k + 2$. If $n - |I| = k$, then G is $K_{k, k+2}$. If $n - |I| = (k + 1)$, then $k \geq 3$ since $n = 2k + 3 \geq 9$. Thus Lemma 4 implies that G has a cycle of length at least $(n - 1)$ and thereby G is traceable, a contradiction. If $n - |I| = (k + 2)$, then $k \geq 3$ since $n = 2k + 3 \geq 9$. Thus Lemma 3 implies that G is Hamiltonian and thereby G is traceable, a contradiction.

This completes the proof of [1] in Theorem 3.

Proof of [2] in Theorem 3. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 9$ vertices and e edges satisfying the conditions in [2] in Theorem 3. If $\beta \leq (k + 1)$, then Lemma 2 implies that G is traceable. If $\beta \geq (k + 2)$, then G has an independent set I of size $(k + 2)$. Suppose G is not traceable. we have that $n \geq 2\delta + 2 \geq 2k + 2$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq (n - 1)/2$ and G is traceable. From the conditions in [2] in Theorem 3 and Theorem 1, we have

$$\delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2 \leq M_1(G) \leq \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2.$$

where $\delta_1 = \min\{d(y) : y \in V - I\}$.

Thus

$$M_1(G) = \delta_1 e + |I|\delta^2.$$

Therefore G is a bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $|I| = (k + 1)$, $d(u) = \delta$ for each $u \in I$, and $d(v) = \delta_1$ for each vertex v in $V - I$. Since $\delta|I| = e = (n - |I|)\delta_1$ and $\delta_1 \geq \delta$, we have $n - |I| \leq |I| = k + 2$. Notice that $n - |I| \geq k$, we have that $n - |I| = k$, $n - |I| = (k + 1)$, or $n - |I| = k + 2$. If $n - |I| = k$, then G is $K_{k, k+2}$. If $n - |I| = (k + 1)$, then $k \geq 3$ since $n = 2k + 3 \geq 9$. Thus Lemma 4 implies that G has a cycle of length at least $(n - 1)$ and thereby G is traceable, a contradiction. If $n - |I| = (k + 2)$, then $k \geq 3$ since $n = 2k + 3 \geq 9$. Thus Lemma 3 implies that G is Hamiltonian and thereby G is traceable, a contradiction.

This completes the proof of [2] in Theorem 3.

4 A Corollary

Let I be a maximum independent set in a graph G . Then $|I| = \beta$. Obviously, $\Delta_1 = \max\{d(x) : x \in I\} \leq (n - \beta)$ and $\delta_1 = \min\{d(y) : y \in V - I\} \geq \delta$. Replacing respectively $\Delta_1 = \max\{d(x) : x \in I\}$ and $\delta_1 = \min\{d(y) : y \in V - I\}$ by $(n - \beta)$ and δ in the proofs of Theorem 1, we have the following corollary.

Corollary 1. Let G be a graph with n vertices and e edges. Suppose I is a maximum independent set in G and β is the independence number of G . Then

[1]. $M_1(G) \leq (n - \beta)e + (n - \beta)\Delta^2$ with equality if and only if G is $K_{\beta, n-\beta}$.

[2]. $M_1(G) \geq \delta e + \beta\delta^2$ with equality if and only if G is a regular bipartite graph with partition sets I and $V - I$ such that $|I| = |V - I|$.

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